

Acid Dissociation Constants of the N' -substituted Biguanides and Dibiguanides

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Acid dissociation constants of some of the N' -substituted biguanides and dibiguanides have been determined by Bjerrum's method and the influence of the substitutions in the biguanide molecule on its basic character has been discussed.

Das Sarma (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 217) and also Sengupta and Rây (*ibid.*, 1960, 37, 303) have determined the acid dissociation constants (basic strength) of biguanide and several N' -substituted biguanides and $N'N'$ -dibiguanides. The determination of the acid dissociation constant of some N' -substituted biguanides, not previously examined, have been described here. This affords a wider range of a comparative study of the influence of substituted groups in N' -position of the biguanide on their basic properties.

Being diacidic bases, N' -substituted biguanides can combine with one or two H^+ to form conjugated acids, $R\text{-BigH}_2^+$ and $R\text{-BigH}_3^{2+}$ corresponding to the salts $R\text{-BigH}\cdot HX$ and $R\text{-BigH}\cdot 2HX$ (where $R\text{-BigH}$ = one molecule of N' -substituted biguanide and HX = a monobasic acid).

Therefore,

and

Hence k_{a_1} and k_{a_2} may be represented (Das Sarma, *loc. cit.*) as

$$k_{a_1} = \frac{[R\text{-BigH}][H^+]}{[R\text{-BigH}_2^+]}$$

and

$$k_{a_2} = \frac{[R\text{-BigH}_2^+][H^+]}{[R\text{-BigH}_3^{2+}]}$$

The values of k_{a_1} and k_{a_2} are obtained from the formation curves (Fig. 1)* obtained by plotting $\bar{\eta}$ against the pH values when $\bar{\eta} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively (cf. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", P. Haase and Sons; Copenhagen, 1941; Das Sarma, *loc. cit.*).

* Only a few representative curves have been presented,

Hexamethylenedibiguanide, on the other hand, forms salts of the type, $[\text{Hex}(\text{BigH})_2] \cdot 4\text{HX}$, showing a maximum acidity of four. Hence the reaction between the base and the proton may be represented as:

where $\text{A} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6)_2$ and AH^+ , AH_2^{2+} , AH_3^{3+} , and AH_4^{4+} are the ions of the mono-, di-, tri- and tetra-acid salts respectively. The values of k_{a_1} , k_{a_2} , k_{a_3} , and k_{a_4} are obtained from the formation curve (Fig. 2) where $\bar{\eta} = 0.5, 1.5, 2.5$, and 3.5 respectively (cf. Das Sarma, *loc. cit.*).

FIG. 1. Curves A-C represent respectively benzyl, *p*-tolyl, and cyclohexyl-biguanide.

These values can also be obtained from the following relations (cf. Das Sarma, *loc. cit.*):

1. When $(C_H - C'_H) < C_A$ and the formation of cationic

acid higher than AH^+ being negligible, we have $k_{a1} = \frac{[C_A - C_H + C'_H]}{[C_H - C'_H]} \cdot [H^+]$

2. When $(C_H - C'_H) > C_A < 2C_A$, we have $k_{a2} = \frac{[2C_A - C_H + C'_H]}{[C_H - C'_H - C_A]} \cdot [H^+]$

([A] and acids higher than AH_2^{2+} may be neglected).

3. Similarly, when $(C_H - C'_H) > 2C_A < 3C_A$, we have $k_{a3} = \frac{[3C_A - C_H + C'_H]}{[C_H - C'_H - 2C_A]} \cdot [H^+]$

4. When $(C_H - C'_H) > 3C_A < 4C_A$, we have $k_{a4} = \frac{[4C_A - C_H + C'_H]}{[C_H - C'_H - 3C_A]} \cdot [H^+]$

where C_H = concentration of the total acid added, C'_H = concentration of the total acid present in the mixture at equilibrium (obtained from *pH* values), and C_A = total ligand taken.

FIG. 2. Hexamethylenedibiguanide.

The acid dissociation constant values of these biguanides are recorded in Tables II and III for comparison. On comparing the value of the first acid dissociation, k_{a1} (basic strength), of the biguanide and substituted biguanides, it may be concluded that biguanide and its *N*'-mono- or dialkylbiguanides are stronger bases than the aryl-substituted ones. Benzylbiguanide behaves like alkylbiguanides in this respect. This also holds good of the cyclohexylbiguanide. On the contrary, *p*-tolyl- and phenethylbiguanides have values similar to phenylbiguanides. In the case of the dibiguanides, the ethylene- and hexamethylene-dibiguanides are stronger bases than the *m*-phenylenedibiguanide.

The alkylbiguanides may be arranged in the ascending order of their basic character as: butylⁿ < propylⁿ = propylⁱ < ethylhexyl < hexylⁿ = methyl < ethyl < dimethyl < diethyl.

The hydroxyl group, when present in the alkyl radical, increases the basicity of the ligand, whereas the methoxyl group present in the same position as that of the hydroxyl group decreases the basicity and shows almost the same value of k_{a_1} as that of the corresponding alkybiguanide (Sengupta and Rây *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Propylⁿ -, propylⁱ -and butylⁿ -biguanide acid sulphates were obtained by heating the requisite amine, dicyandiamide, and copper sulphate on a water bath, treating with H₂SO₄ (dil.), then with H₂S, and finally by concentration and cooling.

TABLE I

Materials	F o u n d.			C a l c u l a t e d.		
	N.	Anion.	H ₂ O.	N.	Anion.	H ₂ O.
1. Propyl ⁿ biguanide acid sulphate, C ₃ H ₇ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆ .H ₂ SO ₄	28.96%	39.62%	..	29.05%	39.83	..
2. Propyl ⁱ biguanide acid sulphate, C ₃ H ₇ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆ .H ₂ SO ₄ .H ₂ O	27.45	37.40	..	27.13	37.20	..
3. Butyl ⁿ biguanide acid sulphate, C ₄ H ₉ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆ .H ₂ SO ₄	27.20	37.44	..	27.45	37.65	..
4. Hexyl ⁿ biguanide sulphate, (C ₆ H ₁₃ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆) ₂ .H ₂ SO ₄ .2H ₂ O (Dutta, <i>Z. anorg. Chem.</i> , 1959, 302, 237)	27.45	19.06	7.12	27.78	19.01	7.14%
5. 2-Ethylhexylbiguanide acid sulphate, (C ₈ H ₁₈ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆).H ₂ SO ₄ .1.5H ₂ O (Dutta and Lahiry, <i>Z. anorg. Chem.</i> , in press).	20.95	28.13	8.48	20.71	28.40	8.00
6. Cyclohexylbiguanide acid sulphate, (C ₆ H ₁₁ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆).H ₂ SO ₄ (Dutta and Lahiry, <i>loc.cit.</i>)	25.17	34.58	..	24.91	34.16	..
7. <i>p</i> -Tolylbiguanide hydrochloride, C ₇ H ₇ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆ .HCl (Ghosh and Chatterjee, <i>this Journal</i> , 1955, 32, 222)	..	15.75	..	15.60	..	..
8. Benzylbiguanide acid sulphate, C ₇ H ₇ .C ₂ N ₅ H ₆ .H ₂ SO ₄ (Rây, <i>Z. anorg. Chem.</i> , in press)	..	33.01	..	..	33.33	..
9. <i>p</i> -Phenylbiguanide hydrochloride C ₈ H ₉ O.C ₂ N ₅ H ₆ .HCl (Ghosh and Banerjee, <i>this Journal</i> , 1955, 32, 32)	..	13.82	..	..	13.78	..
10. Hexamethylenedibiguanide acid sulphate, (C ₆ H ₁₂ .C ₄ N ₁₀ H ₁₂).2H ₂ SO ₄ (Dutta, <i>this Journal</i> , 1960, 37, 32)	27.89	38.20	3.15	28.11	38.55	3.01

The biguanide hydrochloride solutions were prepared from their corresponding sulphate and BaCl₂ solution in calculated quantities. All of these were of 0.05M strength with respect to the ligand concerned.

Alkali solutions used were prepared from caustic soda of Merck's analytical variety with a little BaCl₂ solution to remove any carbonate present. The alkali solutions were standardised against dried hydrazine sulphate. Hydrochloric acid solution was standardised against standard alkali and also by determination of chlorine as AgCl. All the vessels employed were of Jena glass and all solutions were made with conductivity water.

Procedure.—0.05M Biguanide hydrochloride solution (10 c.c.) was taken in each of a number of 50 c.c. volumetric flasks and varying amounts of standard HCl or alkali solutions were added to the flasks; the volume was made to 50 c.c. The flasks containing the solutions were kept for 24 hours at 30° ± 2°. The values of the solutions were measured by using universal glass electrode (Cambridge) against a saturated calomel reference electrode. The values of k_{a1} and k_{a2} were obtained from the $\bar{\eta}$ values plotted against pH. The results are recorded in Table II, which also includes the corresponding values of other ligands previously studied.

TABLE II

Acid dissociation constants of hexamethylenedibiguanide.

$C_A = 0.005M$				Temp. = 32° ± 2°		
C_H	pH.	C'_H	$C_H - C'_H$	$\bar{\eta}$	Acid dis. const.	
I. ($C_H - C'_H$) < (C_A).						
0.00112M	11.71	..	0.00112M	0.22	k_{a1} {	
0.00171	11.61	..	0.00171	0.34		7.90×10^{-12} *
0.00230	11.55	..	0.00230	0.46		4.61×10^{-12}
0.00289	11.50	..	0.00289	0.58		3.36×10^{-12}
0.00348	11.41	..	0.00348	0.70		2.39×10^{-12}
II. ($C_H - C'_H$) > C_A < 2 C_A .						
0.00584	11.15	..	0.00584	1.17	k_{a2} {	
0.00643	11.06	..	0.00643	1.28		3.48×10^{-11} *
0.00702	10.92	..	0.00702	1.40		2.17×10^{-11}
0.00761	10.75	..	0.00761	1.52		1.80×10^{-11}
0.00820	10.65	..	0.00820	1.64		1.62×10^{-11}
III. ($C_H - C'_H$) > 2 C_A < 3 C_A .						
0.01065	8.24	..	0.010650	2.11	k_{a3} {	
0.01174	6.75	..	0.011740	2.35		..*
0.01233	3.60	0.000251	0.012079	2.42		..*
0.01292	3.52	0.000302	0.012620	2.52		12.5×10^{-4}
0.01351	3.38	0.000417	0.013093	2.62		12.7×10^{-4}
0.01410	2.66	0.002198	0.014272	2.85		12.6×10^{-4}
0.01764	2.53	0.002951	0.014689	2.94		13.7×10^{-4}
IV. ($C_H - C'_H$) > 3 C_A < 4 C_A .						
0.02000	2.46	0.003487	0.016533	3.30		k_{a4} {
0.02100	2.40	0.003981	0.017021	3.41	7.91×10^{-3}	
0.02401	2.26	0.005495	0.018513	3.70	5.88×10^{-3}	
0.02637	2.14	0.007079	0.019293	3.86	2.37×10^{-3}	
0.02856	2.06	0.008710	0.019788	3.95	1.14×10^{-3}	
	k_{a1}	k_{a2}	k_{a3}	k_{a4}		
Graphical	..	2.88×10^{-12}	1.78×10^{-11}	3.2×10^{-4}	5.25×10^{-3}	
Calculated	..	3.00×10^{-12}	1.72×10^{-11}	3.1×10^{-4}	4.32×10^{-3}	

N.B. In taking the mean of the calculated k_a values we have omitted the border line values (marked*).

TABLE III

Biguanides.	$k_{a1} \times 10^{12}$.	$k_{a2} \times 10^3$.	Reference.
1. Unsubstituted	3.02	1.167	Das Sarma
2. Methyl	3.63	1.000	"
3. Ethyl	3.39	0.832	"
4. Dimethyl	3.02	1.69	"
5. Diethyl	2.09	2.93	"
6. Propyl ⁿ	4.47	0.79	Present authors
7. Propyl ⁱ	4.47	0.79	"
8. Butyl ⁿ	5.25	1.20	"
9. Hexyl ⁿ	3.63	0.50	"
10. Ethylhexyl	3.98	0.79	"
11. Cyclohexyl	4.07	0.63	"
12. Ethanol	2.98	1.58	Sengupta and Rây
13. Propanol	3.16	1.00	"
14. Methoxyethyl	3.38	1.00	"
15. Methoxypropyl	3.98	0.83	"
16. Phenyl	19.05	6.92	Das Sarma
17. Benzyl	5.62	1.99	Present authors
18. <i>p</i> -Tolyl	14.40	2.51	"
19. <i>p</i> -Phenetyl	15.10	1.99	"
20. α -Naphthyl	5.75	8.85	Das Sarma

Dibiguanides.	k_{a1} .	k_{a2} .	k_{a3} .	k_{a4} .	
1. Ethylene	1.74×10^{-12}	4.57×10^{-12}	1.32×10^{-3}	1.82×10^{-2}	Das Sarma
2. Hexamethylene	2.88×10^{-12}	1.78×10^{-11}	0.32×10^{-3}	5.25×10^{-3}	Present authors
3. <i>m</i> -Phenylene	4.07×10^{-12}	1.35×10^{-10}	7.03×10^{-3}	3.92×10^{-2}	Das Sarma

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